

Apex Bank Intervention and Agricultural Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

The Nigerian apex bank's agricultural intervention has continued to have a substantial influence on the growth of the agricultural sector, primarily through mobilizing credit facilities for the country's small, medium, and large-scale commercial farmers. The study shows that the apex bank also aided the industry by using loan guarantees to handle default concerns, with the goal of encouraging commercial financial institutions to do business with agricultural business owners. The research does, however, include the Central Bank of Nigeria's intervention facilities for agricultural growth in Nigeria.

Keywords: Development, Central Bank of Nigeria, agriculture, and finance

Introduction

The nutrition transition in malnutrition in the developing world today is quite complicated by a shift away from traditional diets towards a more globalized intake pattern that includes increased quantities of processed foods, animal products, sugars, fats, and alcohol . High rates of food insecurity and malnutrition as well as the prevalence of overweight and associated non-communicable diseases, are leading to a "double burden." It's expedient that governments and multilateral agencies boost food production. This is being pursued with different agricultural programmes, including the need to migrate to provide intervention funds to many developing entities.

Since agricultural growth and transformation in Nigeria are dependent on sustained public sector interventions, commercial agriculture

involves the considerable application of modern techniques, including machinery and other farm input but the capital equipment significance has grossly reduced the number of labour and capital productivity. Development financing is one of the major instruments for rapid and sustainable economic growth and development, which supply finance, fund, credit and donations to various sectors of the economy to achieve welfare improvement, greater productivity and facilitate economic growth. Development finance is the financial initiatives involving formulating and implementing policies, innovations, schemes, programmes, and appropriate financial supply/credit to deliver economic services effectively, efficiently, and sustainably to achieve economic growth and development.

In Nigeria, the highest financial regulatory

body is the central bank which has been playing this development finance role in supporting the sectors of the economy such as agriculture, industry and entrepreneurs with the supply of finance, credits and donations for the growth and development of the Nigeria economy. The Central Bank of Nigeria is the sole designer, initiator, administrator and regulator of all development finance policies and schemes in Nigeria. All the internal financial institutions, lending institutions, development finance institutions and commercial banks are controlled, guided and operated under the central bank of Nigeria's directives. The Central Bank of Nigeria's development finance role initiatives involves the participation of Central Bank Nigeria directly or indirectly in the economy in terms of the formulation and implementation of various policies, schemes, programmes innovations and directives for the provision of sufficient finance and credit to the productive sectors of Nigeria with the primary objective of facilitating economic growth and development . Thus, structural issues such as low access to finance for real sector investment, non-diversification of the economic base in export earnings, inadequate infrastructure, financial exclusion and unemployment persist. Addressing these challenges requires robust policies directly targeting identified sectors that have weighty implications for national economic growth and development. It's against this backdrop that this study intends to investigate the influence of the central bank of Nigeria on intervention facilities for agricultural export commodities development in Nigeria.

However, Nigeria, like most other African countries, is not only endowed with vast agricultural farmland but also a conducive geographical condition that favours agricultural production throughout the year. Despite this great potential, there is little to show for it .

Poor credit supply is one of the factors accounting for the poor performance of the agricultural sector in Nigeria. Meanwhile, commercial, financial institutions have no kin interest in financing agriculture. To encourage these banks, the government established several agricultural credit schemes to provide guarantees against inherent risk in agricultural lending . Consequently, the country, with its highly diversified agroecological condition is relying on massive importation of basic food items and raw materials for industrial inputs . The resultant effect of the high cost of living coupled with a high level of unemployment on the common man is beyond reasonable imagination.

Against this backdrop, the study investigated the influence of the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) intervention policies on agricultural development in Nigeria. Thus, the extent of how much input in form of financial support accruing as a consequence utilized to the agricultural development in Nigeria cannot be said to be ascertained.

Review of Related Literature

Finance is critical to the day-to-day operations of any organisation; thus, its importance cannot be overstated. Finance is the foundation for obtaining capital assets for a business, such as land, machinery, buildings, and any other assets

required for the start of a successful corporate business . Furthermore, money is the lifeblood of an agricultural business, which is primarily concerned in the production, processing, marketing, and delivery of food, and improved access to required funding would aid in its expansion and quick growth.

Agricultural activities are dominated by peasant smallholder farmers, who account for around 90% of agricultural holdings in Nigeria. These farmers mostly use traditional methods and produce primarily for subsistence. Agriculture is regarded as a fundamental pillar of the Nigerian economy. Its importance in terms of economic growth and sustainable development, employment opportunities, poverty alleviation, and export cannot be overstated . The agriculture sector encourages structural reform and economic diversification. It allows the economy to fully use its factor endowment. It also ensures that the country is less reliant on foreign agricultural supplies .

Hitherto, Nigeria had an agrarian economy, with agriculture as the foundation of growth. Agriculture was a significant source of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) shortly after independence. It produced over 70% of the GDP and employed a considerable proportion of the working population. The industry also accounted for almost 90% of all foreign exchange earnings and government income. During this time, Nigeria rose to become the world's second biggest cocoa producer and a net exporter and producer of palm oil, cotton, groundnuts, hides, and rubber. Following the discovery of oil, this situation began to deteriorate.

Between 1970 and 1974, the proportion of agricultural exports to total exports deteriorated from forty-three per cent to about seven per cent. This was largely due to the oil price hikes of 1973 – 1974. This, however resulted in a huge income of foreign exchange and the consequent neglect of agriculture. From the 1970s to the 1980s, agricultural exports declined by seventeen per cent annually . During the 1980s, the agricultural sector could no longer meet local food requirements, and supply raw materials for industry and had lost its foreign exchange earning capacity. This was attributed to several socio-economic and environmental challenges. Domestic food supply had since become a major challenge in Nigeria, and huge foreign exchange earnings were utilized in importing food. Consequently, Nigeria has been witnessing extreme hunger and poverty due to the lack of basic food items.

The challenges of the agricultural economy could be traced to the increased dependence on oil and the consequent neglect of agriculture. After the discovery of oil, the agricultural sector's percentage contribution to GDP nosedived and fluctuated between 10-22 percent from 1980 to 2015 . However, according to the Statista report, the contribution of agriculture to Nigeria's GDP increased between 2019 - 2021, contributing about 30 percent to the GDP in 2021

The effect of this is directly noticed by smallholder farmers. Smallholder farmers are majorly subsistence farmers, and they produce the majority of the food in Nigeria. They produce eighty-five percent of total agricultural production and reside mainly in rural areas. Their

productive capacity and growth are, however, hindered by inadequate and inaccessible credit facilities.

A scholar explains that agriculture constitutes a very important sector of the Nigerian economy and was the dominant sector before the crude oil boom of the 1970's. He stresses that the agricultural sector contributes 64.1 per cent of the gross domestic product as compared to other sectors. The Nigerian agricultural sector is characterized by a low farm income, a low level of capacity to satisfy the food and fibre need of the country and primitive techniques of production. The nature of the problem of the agricultural sector boils down to financial constraints. At the heart of the financial problem, is the despondence of small farmers in the Nigerian rural economy; about 90% require fairly small size loans. Agricultural finance plays a very important role in agricultural productivity and development. The provision of credit has been adjudged as a critical resource in the advancement of the agricultural sector. However, access to agricultural finance has been seriously incapacitated in Nigeria.

Literature suggested that increased credit availability would result in increased agricultural production, a lower unemployment rate, and greater earnings. It was estimated that barely 5% of farmers in Nigeria and roughly 15% in Asia and Latin America had access to formal loans.

The Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) was founded in 1977 in an attempt to address this situation. The fund was created to encourage banks to boost their agricultural lending and advances. As a result, the

fund's purpose was to provide assurances against the negative risks of agricultural loans. However, between 1981 and 2015, the ACGSF only insured loans totalling N75.5 billion. From 1981 to 2016, commercial banks' direct lending to the agriculture industry was valued at N3.48 trillion. Also, from 1981-2016, Government capital expenditure on agriculture was valued at N1.19 trillion, and Government recurrent expenditure on agriculture was valued at N525.11 billion, respectively.

As such, it was imperative to determine whether agricultural funding had stimulated the agricultural sector's performance in Nigeria. Interventions by the government have been influenced by the need to provide access to inputs and other support to peasant farmers to boost their productivity and enable them transit to mechanized agricultural practices. In contrast, commercial farm holders were supported through the provision of credit facilities, input subsidies, capacity-building initiatives and export incentives.

Theoretical Framework

The commercial loan theory of liquidity was employed to give credence to the study.

Commercial Loan Theory of Liquidity

The Commercial loan theory of liquidity also known as the real bills doctrine was developed by Adam Smith in 1776. Adam Smith uses this theory to explain the bank liquidity that short-term loans advanced to finance saleable goods on the way from producer to consumer are the most liquid loans the bank can make. These are self-liquidating loans because the goods being

financed will soon be sold. The loan finances a transaction and the transaction itself provides the borrower with the funds to repay the bank. According to Adam Smith these loans are liquid because their purpose and their collateral were liquid. The goods move quickly from the producers through the distributors to the retail outlet and then are purchased by the ultimate cash-paying consumer.

The theory stipulates that commercial banks should only lend to profitable business organizations for a short-term period and ensure the loans can self-liquidate. A loan is self-liquidating if the loan finances a transaction and the transaction in return generates the funds to repay the loan. The Real Bills Doctrine can easily be illustrated as a transaction between a bank and a business that creates money in the economy. For example, a seed company supplies One Hundred Thousand Naira (N100,000) worth of maize seeds to a farmer. An invoice is written with payment due in 90 days. The farmer agrees to repay the credit after planting, harvesting, processing and sales over the 90 days period. In effect, the supplier has created commercial paper (a "real bill" that is not secured but represents tangible goods in the process) that has a value of One Hundred Thousand Naira (N100,000). Rather than wait to be paid, the supplier can sell the paper to a bank at its present discounted value of, say, Ninety-Eight Thousand Naira (N98, 000). The bank monetizes the paper, and the bill is collected at full value.

The theory also posits that the composition of commercial banks' assets should consist primarily of loans advanced to business

organizations for their working capital. This theory postulates that if commercial banks limit their advances to productive, self-liquidating, short-term liquidating loans; the central bank should also limit their advances to banks' on the security of those short-term loans. This principle would ensure the liquidity of the commercial banks and an adequate supply of money for the economy.

The Central Bank increases or reduces bank reserves by rediscounting approved loans when a business expands or declines and the volume of trade increases or reduces respectively. Commercial banks provide funds to the agricultural sector by granting loans to farmers to finance their working capital needs.

The liquidation of the loans is expected to come from the production, distribution and sale of their farm produce. Some economists have however criticized the doctrine. The economists that advocated the quantity theory suggested that central banks should focus on stabilizing the quantity of money, preferring active open-market policies like the acquisition of public debt to drive liquidity in markets and stabilize the currency. The doctrine was most strongly criticized by economists supporting free banking. They argued that the government shouldn't be involved in money supply management. They opined that open commercial competition provides the optimal stabilization of money creation.

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Intervention and Agricultural Development

The Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) monetary,

credit, international trade, and exchange rate policies have all worked well to keep inflation and currency rate depreciation under control. However, structural difficulties such as limited access to credit for real sector investment, a lack of diversification of the economic base in terms of export profits, insufficient infrastructure, financial exclusion, and unemployment persist. To address these difficulties, strong policies that directly target specific industries and value chains with significant consequences for national economic growth and development are required.

Section 31 of the CBN Act No. 7 of 2007 (as amended) authorizes the bank to carry out developmental functions such as encouraging the development of Nigeria's money or capital markets or fostering financial or economic growth. The CBN's development role is meant to decrease financial market failure through appropriate actions that enhance the supply side's capacity to effectively intermediary and the demand side's capacity to absorb financial services optimally. The Bank's developmental function is carried out through a development finance policy.

The CBN commenced development finance in 1964 when it began supporting the then commodities boards as ordered by the Federal Government of Nigeria. By 2009-2010, the Bank has made a significant number of development funding operations. This was justified by the necessity to stimulate the economy following the global financial crises of 2007-2008. Another important phase was 2015-2016 when the Bank implemented a number of measures to help the real sector and bring the economy out of a slump.

It is worth noting that these initiatives are not exclusive to the CBN. It is the standard of central banks in developing countries, even high-income countries.

Agriculture, industry, manufacturing, and other associated economic sectors in Nigeria lack access to sufficient and equitable finance that would allow them to enhance their inputs and output. As a result, the Central Bank of Nigeria's credit schemes were formed and aimed to boost the inflow of appropriate and just credit to Nigeria's productive sectors, mostly at single and set interest rates. The Central Bank of Nigeria's development role initiatives entails the Central Bank of Nigeria's participation in the economy, either directly or indirectly, in the formulation and implementation of various policies, schemes, programmes, innovations, and directives for the provision of sufficient finance and credit to Nigeria's productive sectors, with the primary goal of facilitating economic growth and development.

In order to accelerate the nation's economy and facilitate agricultural development and economic progress, the Central Bank of Nigeria is adopting different reforms, such as credit schemes and financial programmes, that have a direct influence on the country's economy. The Central Bank of Nigeria's Development Finance Department is driving these fundamental changes to accomplish microeconomic goals such as quick and balanced economic development and eliminating poverty, unemployment, and inequality.

Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme

The Central Bank of Nigeria manages development funding through credit schemes such as the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme, which was formed in 1977 to revitalise and enhance the agricultural sector by providing loans to Nigeria's small and medium rural farmers. The credit scheme was designed primarily to improve food production and food security and address the issues that rural farmers growing food crops have due to a lack of access to appropriate and equitable credit facilities. According to data from the Central Bank of Nigeria, the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme has provided financial assistance to farmers in Nigeria totalling 130.90 billion naira from its inception through the first quarter of 2022.

Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACCS)

The Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACCS) was created to accelerate the growth of the agricultural value sector of the economy by providing credit facilities to large-scale commercial farmers at single-digit interest rates. The strategy boosts agricultural commercialization, modernisation, mechanisation, large-scale agricultural output, agricultural export commodities, foreign exchange revenues, and Nigeria's commercial agricultural-oriented industry. Furthermore, according to statistics from the Central Bank of Nigeria's economic report, as of the first quarter of 2022, a total of 735.17 billion had been given to farmers under the Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACCS) to further accelerate agricultural growth in Nigeria.

Nigerian Incentive-Based Risk Sharing in Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL)

In addition to the Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACCS) is, the Nigerian Incentive-Based Risk Sharing in Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL) established to mobilize financing for Nigerian agri-business through the use of credit guarantees to address the risks associated with default and targeted at encouraging financial institutions to be more receptive to doing business with agri-businesses. NIRSAL was aimed at creating greater access to finance through the integration of end-to-end agriculture value chains such as input producers, farmers, agro-dealers, agro-processors and industrial manufacturers with agricultural financing value chains – loan product development, credit distribution, loan origination, managing and pricing for risk, and loan disbursement. The integration was driven by the NIRSAL's 5 pillars, particularly the Risk Sharing Pillar and the Technical Assistance pillars, such as Risk Sharing Facility, N45 billion; Insurance Facility, N4.5 billion; Technical Assistance Facility, N9 billion; Agricultural.

Impacts of the CBN's Intervention Fund on Agricultural Development in Nigeria

The interventions by the CBN in the agricultural sector are principally anchored on the selected programmes, such as; Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme (ACGS) and the Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACCS), among others. Examining the impact of the interventions in the agricultural sector is based

on the assumption that such interventions impact the production decisions of agricultural business owners leading to increased output/ yield. Given that the interventions by the Bank are provided to both small and large-scale agriculturalists, it is plausible to assume that those interventions act as increases in the stock of agricultural capital and thus have direct effects on the production decisions of the farmers. However, the efforts of the CBN have contributed to the nation's agricultural sector immensely and Nigeria's GDP all-around since its inception. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) stated that the contribution of the agricultural sector to the GDP rose from 19.79 in 2015 to 22.35 in Q1 (2021). Also, 2.2 percent real growth was recorded in Nigeria's agricultural sector in Q4 of 2020. This has helped Nigeria's economy to record its first growth in three quarters. Hence, the role of the CBN intervention efforts and development finance activities as a factor in the agricultural growth of the country.

The report from the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics indicated that the agricultural sector topped the chart in a survey of seven sectors identified to have contributed to Nigeria's economy in the second quarter of 2022. The chart revealed that agriculture alone contributed 23.3 percent to GDP (Half Year 2022), which supports the positive trend of the previous years' performance of 25.88 percent (2021); 26.21 per cent (2020); 25.16 percent (2019); 25.13 percent (2018); 25.08 per cent (2017); 24.45 percent (2016) and 23.11 percent (2015) . Furthermore, Yusuf Yila, the CBN Director of Department of Finance, stated that the Central Bank of Nigeria's

efforts and interventions have resulted in a lot of development and effect, ranging from combating extreme poverty, food insecurity, and growing the agricultural sector and manufacturing base. He added that food security in Nigeria has improved dramatically in the last five years. The CBN intervention has further reduced the dependency on imported foodstuffs.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study reveals that the CBN interventions in agriculture have ensured positive trends of performances to the country's GDP. However, the CBN is expected to play an increasingly important role against the background of previous gross under-performances. To keep up with this expectation, it will need to transform in ownership, management, human capital, organization, the scope of operation, processes, and resources. However, these cannot happen without the buy-in and support of its current owners.

With the required government (ownership) support and open-mindedness to partial privatization, reforms and modernization, the Bank will achieve good and sustainable financial performance; and good socio-economic behaviour, through rapid, sustainable and inclusive growth, wealth and job creation, food security (the beginning of true independence and national self-respect) diversified and stable economy, foreign exchange earnings through increased export, foreign exchange conservation through import substitution agric-led industrialization, inexpensive local raw material for industry, and increased FDI.

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